

GENE NAME	GENE ID	GenBank ACCESSION NUMBER	⁽⁵⁾ FORWARD PRIMER ⁽³⁾	⁽⁵⁾ REVERSE PRIMER ⁽³⁾
<i>NoDGTT1</i>	CCMP1779_4340	KY273668	ATGTACCCAATCAAGCTGTGCTTCCTC	TCACTTAATAAGCAGCTTCTTGCCG
<i>NoDGTT2</i>	CCMP1779_3705	KY273669	ATGGCTCACCTCTTCCGTCG	AGAGATCGCAACGAACTCCTCG
<i>NoDGTT3</i>	CCMP1779_7206	KY273670	ATGGGCGCTACCACCGAGACCCA GACTAAA	CGACTTCGGACAGTCCCAAATCTC CAACTCTCGCGT
<i>NoDGTT4</i>	CCMP1779_9929	KY273671	ATGAAGCGGGCGGCAGCA	GCAGCGTCGCGACTGGTCT
<i>NoDGTT5</i>	CCMP1779_3915	KY273672	ATGACGCCGCAAGCCGACATCACC AGCAAGACGA	CTCAATGGACAACGGGCGCGTCTC CCACTCC
<i>NoDGTT6</i>	CCMP1779_9590	KY273673	ATGTCCTCCTTCTTGCGTTGGC	GCTATTATTCTTACCGCTGCTACTGC

Table S2. Primers used for amplification of *NoDGTT1-NoDGTT6* full sequences for cloning into pYES2.1/V5-His-TOPO[®] vector.